

THE IMPORTANCE AND USAGE OF TASK BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING AND SEQUENCING FOR B2 LEVEL PHILOLOGY AND NON-PHILOLOGY FACULTY STUDENTS

Tojimatov Rasuljon¹

Abdug'offorov Sardorbek²

Tox'taboyeva Yodgora³

Tojimatova Madina⁴

¹EFL teacher of NamCI

^{2,3,4}Master's students of NamSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406939>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st March 2022

Accepted: 10th March 2022

Online: 14th March 2022

KEY WORDS

task based, language teaching, TBLT, B2 level students, teaching methodology, in English language classroom

ABSTRACT

this article defines that usage of task based language teaching and sequencing for B2 level philology and non-philology faculty students. There are many ideas for giving various tasks for B2 level students in English language classroom in different directions.

Task-based language teaching (TBLT) increasingly informs the design and implementation of national language curricula in many parts of the world. Reflecting this real world relevance, scholarship in the field has increasingly taken an eco-logical perspective, focusing on the role of context in mediating the way teachers interpret the practice of. This recent orientation towards the particular stands in synergistic contrast to a well-established experimental/quasi-experimental research tradition focusing on tasks rather than teachers, on learning rather than learners, and on conditions rather than context. It also aligns with M. H. Long's contention that "true" TBLT is only ever derived from a situated needs analysis, ensuring that tasks are, by definition, local and specific. For this reason, Long identifies detailed classroom

studies of the ways teachers and students perform classroom lessons for B2 level students. The study reported in this chapter reflects this classroom orientation. Investigates the fertility of the ground for task-based teaching in a context hitherto under-researched from a TBLT perspective, namely EFL classes in B2 level students' classrooms. In this sector, a new curriculum has recently been rolled out, designed explicitly to improve the English communication skill development of learners. The implementation of this new curriculum relies heavily on mandated text-books which are designed centrally and provided to teachers and students in different faculties as philology and non-philology. Teachers are expected to follow the textbook closely as is the common practice in primary school EFL across Asia. Naturally then, the role and nature of the

textbook is a central consideration in research into instructional practices in these contexts.

In the last 30 years, there has been an enormous interest by researchers, language professionals and practicing teachers worldwide in task-based language teaching (TBLT) as an approach to second/foreign language (L2) learning and teaching and a teaching methodology in which classroom tasks constitute the main focus of instruction. This is evidenced by the numerous publications, symposiums, seminars, colloquiums, academic sessions, conference presentations and indeed whole conferences that are specifically dedicated to TBLT (Van den Branden, Bygate and Norris 2009). The most notable of these is the formation of the International Consortium on Task-based Language Teaching (ICTBLT) in 2005 which holds a biennial international conference on the topic, now transformed into a professional association, named International Association for Task-Based Language Teaching (IATBLT). The most

recent TBLT conference was held in Barcelona. Virtually all of these publications, professionals, and academic professional events speak of the potential value of TBLT for L2 learning and teaching. Based on insights from second language acquisition (SLA) research findings, empirical findings on effective instructional techniques, and cognitive psychology, it is strongly believed that TBLT facilitates SLA and makes L2 learning and teaching more principled and more effective.

To sum up, there are theoretical grounds, and empirical evidence, for believing that tasks might be able to offer all the affordances needed for successful instructed language development, whoever the learners might be and whatever the context. Van den Branden et al. have based these conclusions on the extensive and varied literature on task-based learning, teaching and assessment, which speaks to the potential of TBLT as an approach to L2 learning and teaching and as a teaching methodology.

References:

1. Newton and Trang Bui, Victoria University of Wellington DOI 10.1515/9781501503399-013 Jonathan
2. Mohammad Javad Ahmadian and María del Pilar García Mayo <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781501503399-001>
3. Mohammad Javad Ahmadian, University of Leeds María del Pilar García Mayo, Universidad del País Vasco (UPV/EHU)
4. Zhisheng (Edward) Wen, Macao Polytechnic Institute DOI 10.1515/9781501503399-003
5. Van den Branden et al. 2009: Victoria University of Wellington DOI 10.1515/9781501503399-013 Jonathan
6. Griffiths, C. & Parr, J. M. (2001). Language Learning Strategies: Theory and Perception. *ELT Journal*, 55(3), 247-254.